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Opportunities and challenges for research data infrastructures (national archives/data services) in current non-CESSDA member countries

- “Widening the European infrastructure for Social Science data archives”
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- 3rd and 4th May, Lisbon Portugal

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An introduction to cessda saw

*Task 3.2 Audit of current status of
data archive services in each ERA country
and assessment of potential for development*

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Content of the session

- Introduction, overview of task 3.2 aims and results
- Special focus on DAS protoactivities, initiatives
- Presentation of selected countries (to illustrate the approach and to show promising development):
 - Serbia, FYR Macedonia, Italy
- Discussion

Introduction:

Aims of the Audit of current status of data archive services in each ERA country

- To identify gaps for further development of data archives services (DAS) in each country.
- To identifies promising candidate services (where now the research data infrastructure is only emerging), and
- To assess each country potentials for CESSDA membership

The „self-assessment“ method

- An audit was conducted, based on a comprehensive data collection instrument:
 - Web form with closed ended and open ended follow up questions for comments and explanations
- Multiple sources of information were utilised:
 - via self-assessment, as reported by DAS representatives;
 - from desk research of reports resulting from previous surveys or case studies in the research community projects (CESSDA PPP, SERSCIDA, DASISH etc.);
 - or from country and scientific community representatives' expert interviews. (if no contact established with potential DAS)

Participating partners in SaW Task 3.2

- ADP (lead), FFZG, IEN, SND, UKDA, FORS, NSD, DANS as editorial group for data collection and reporting
- Most other SaW partners active in arranging a data collection and in writing country reports (each was responsible for a given number of reports)
- Realisation: Of the 44 ERA countries 37 full reports obtained, 5 has only basic report and 3 are missing.

Content areas addressed

I. Ecosystem of data sharing:

- *„complex system involving data collectors, stewards, and users as well as sponsors and stakeholders; emergent and historical transparent technologies; and ever-growing data along with their myriad associated artefacts. The system must be understood in totality in order to optimize the whole ...“**

*Parsons et al. A conceptual framework for managing very diverse data for complex, interdisciplinary science. Journal of Information Science 37(6) 555–569, DOI: 10.1177/0165551511412705

- comprehensive set of conditions need to be explored in each national setting
- there is no development model that fits for all

II. Organisational setting and service operational profile

- self-assessment of activities of current DAS in each country, following the specification of CESSDA SaW Capability Development Model (CESSDA-CDM)

Data sharing culture and practice

Data sharing and management practices in research

- whether and how researchers provide and can access the data they need, and researchers' attitudes to data sharing in the country

Barriers to data sharing and enablers, incentives for data sharing

- SSH sector position, national and international research data production as a driver for sharing
- Open data policy at EU, national and institutional level and research ethics as enabler for data sharing
- availability (and maturity) of data infrastructure
- established RDM practices
- career progression as a motive for data sharing

Development of research data production in SSH by CESSDA

Membership status

The established traditions in research data production goes hand in hand with the data sharing support infrastructure : there is a supply and the demand for enhanced data management and data access services

Summary RDM policy requirements by CESSDA Membership status

- **High level assessment contain indicators about details of RDM policy requirements: Data management plan; Appropriate place of data deposit defined; Cost for managing the data resources covered as an incentive; Long-term curation**

Conclusions:

- **Not all current CESSDA members are on the *DEVELOPED* level; Many aspiring members has *EMERGING* policy**

Heading concepts values means (0 – Underdeveloped; 1 – Developing; 2 – Developed) by CESSDA membership

- Brian Kleiner, Christina Bornatici

Data Archive Services Proto- Activities

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Data Archive Services Proto-Activities

- This section focuses on countries with no established national data archive services (DAS).
- Main aims:
 - Distinguish countries that are currently more active from the less active ones;
 - Identify the key players involved in DAS-related activities and open access (OA) support activities;
 - Describe the current expertise, availability of technical infrastructure;
 - Describe the current activities and organisational first steps.

Data Archive Services Proto-Activities

DAS-activities overall assessment

Technical infrastructure

Are there existing technical infrastructures (national and/or institutional infrastructures in the social sciences such as repositories, online tools, databases, or online catalogues, etc.) that could possibly be used for or applied to a new DAS?

Organisational activities

Are there any activities in your country towards establishing a DAS for the social sciences?

Hosting institution

Are there institutions that could host a DAS for the social sciences in your country?

Capacity building and training

Are there any existing initiatives to develop the knowledge and skills of people who might be employed at a DAS at some point?

OA-activities overall assessment

OA initiatives

Are there open access (OA) projects or initiatives (e.g. OA promotion) in your country?

Data sharing and OA support services

Are there data support services provided to social science researchers in your country that facilitate data sharing and/or Open Access to research data (regarding for example, data management plans, data preservation, and data access)?

Data Archive Services Proto-Activities

Main results from the online survey

0 = No activities

1 = Basic activities

2 = Advanced activities

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Data Archive Services Proto-Activities

Main results from the online survey – DAS activities

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Aleksandra Bradić Martinović and
Aleksandar Zdravković

**Opportunities and challenges for
research data infrastructures (national
archives/data services) in current
non-CESSDA member countries**

Serbian and Macedonian case

SERSCIDA (2012-2014)

- EC funded FP7: Support for Establishment of National/Regional Social Sciences Data Archives (SERSCIDA)
- CESSDA partners: United Kingdom (UKDA), Switzerland (FORS), Slovenia (ADP), Sweden (SND) & local partners Serbia (IEN), Croatia (FFZG) i Bosnia and Herzegovina (HRC)

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SERSCIDA main results

- Analysis of existing potentials for establishment of data archive in SSH for each country
 - Analysis of laws and regulation in science
 - Assessment of existing infrastructure in SSH
 - Assessment of practice within research community (Survey)
- Workshops (UKDA, ADP, FORS) and working visits (UKDA, ADP, SND)
- Establishment plan, Policy and procedures, web site
- Hardware infrastructure

SEEDS (2015-2017)

- SCOPES: South-Eastern European Data Services (SEEDS); SNSF funding
- CESSDA partners: FORS and ADP, SERSCIDA partners Serbia and Croatia and new partners Macedonia (ISPJR), Albania (IDM), Montenegro (CEMI) and Kosovo* (CPC)
- Project results:
 - Improvement of technical infrastructure
 - Archiving datasets (Dataverse), DANS support
 - RRPP Data Rescue

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Macedonian case

- Macedonia currently has no established Data Archive Service
- Number of DAS proto-activities has been realized, within the SEEDS and the RRPP Data Rescue projects...
- ...by the potential service provider, Institute for Sociological, Political and Juridical Research (ISPJR), Saints Cyril and Methodius University:

Macedonian case

Activities through the SEEDS:

- Analysis of potentials for establishment of DAS
- Development of human resources
- Development of technical infrastructure
- Development of policy documents
- Pro-active and supportive in *CESSDA SaW*
- Raise awareness of designated community
- Gain support of the Ministry in charge
- Archiving several datasets in *SEEDSbase* (RRPP)

Challenges

- Development of data centers is only supported through the international projects and with the CESSDA support
- Lack of support from relevant ministries (!)
 - Heavily dependent on political situation
- Huge budget constraints of the national level ministry
- Ignorance of the scientific community
- Lack of technical support

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Italian case: up-grading existing data service towards CESSDA membership

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Main findings for SSRC in Italy

- RDM policy: not set yet / RDMP underdeveloped
- Data sharing culture: not very common
- Incentives and enablers of data sharing: no law, funding programmes, nor career rewards

But...

- ...data service and infrastructure for SSRC is available!
→ in developing phase

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UniData Bicocca Data Archive

- Established in 2015
- An interdepartemental center of University of Milan Bicocca
- Publically funded through the membership of 7 departments
- Holds about 1000 datasets
- Core data services: curation, preservation, review of data sources, DMP support, dissemination, access / sharing
- 2 people engaged

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Mission and Scope

- *“The main purpose of UniData – Bicocca Data Archive is to provide a solid and multidisciplinary infrastructure to the scientific community in compliance with the directives of the “European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures” (ESFRI) in the field of secondary analysis for the social sciences. /.../ The objective is to establish a new Italian Data Archive for the social sciences*

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Main findings for UniData

- Organizational level: mission, scope, legal regulations are defined, but there is a need for support in legislation and funding (staff and resources) on national level
- Digital object management and technical infrastructure: much is already defined (legal transfer of custody, agreements on rights/responsibilities...), some services still need to be further developed...

Main message...

- On national level financial and political support is needed for service providers to be able to play a role of a national service provider
- And to further develop the expertise and foster reuse of research data.
- In this process CESSDA offers support to aspiring members through training, implementation of standards, common tools, best practice...

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—thanks for your attention!

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